

Impact of Carbon Corrosion and Denitrogenation on the Deactivation of Fe–N–C Catalysts in Alkaline Media

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ABSTRACT: Fe–N–C catalysts are considered an earth-abundant alternative to Pt in cathodes of anion exchange membrane fuel cells, although their stability still requires improvement for further commercialization. The degradation of Fe–N–C during both load cycles and start–stop events must be understood and mitigated to minimize system costs. Several approaches have recently been proposed to improve the durability of Fe active species during the oxygen reduction reaction in acidic media. On the other hand, knowledge of the degradation of Fe–N–C catalysts during start–stop events of anion exchange membrane fuel cells remains scarce. In this work, we use a gas diffusion electrode half-cell coupled with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (GDE-ICP-MS) to quantify the Fe dissolution rates in the potential range between 0.93 and 1.5 V_{RHE} . It is shown that Fe dissolution accelerates with increased anodic potential and temperature, while it is independent of the presence/absence of O_2 . The onset potential of Fe dissolution at room temperature agrees with the reported onset potentials of carbon corrosion and denitrogenation, C and N being oxidized to gaseous CO_x and NO_x species, respectively. This correlation supports that the electrochemical oxidation of the N–C matrix triggers the observed catalyst demetallation in these conditions. Using a set of *ex situ* physicochemical characterization techniques, including spectroscopy and microscopy, the various degrees of degradation under three sets of experimental conditions of interest (O_2 -RT, O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT, where RT = 22 °C and HT = 62 °C) are rationalized. Combining the GDE-ICP-MS technique and post-mortem analyses, this work provides detailed insights into the degradation pathways of various Fe, N, and C species during start–stop events, which may inspire the next generation of durable Fe–N–C catalysts for anion exchange membrane fuel cells.

KEYWORDS: Fe–N–C, carbon corrosion, denitrogenation, AEMFC, Fe dissolution, oxygen reduction reaction

1. INTRODUCTION

In a renewable hydrogen cycle, the intermittently available renewable energy is first converted into chemical energy in the form of H_2 using water electrolyzers, and, on demand, the stored energy is converted back to electric power using polymer electrolyte fuel cells (PEFCs). Both technologies have been developed to a high maturity level and are currently in the early stages of commercialization.¹ Yet, the widespread utilization of fuel cells in stationary and automotive applications is still limited due to the high durability-adjusted cost, which is an estimated cost for a fuel cell system with its lifetime extended to 8000 h by replacing the degraded stack when needed.² Impressive optimizations and a drop in cost have been achieved, e.g., for proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs), where the durability-adjusted cost decreased from 481 US\$ kW_{net}^{-1} in 2006 to 76 US\$ kW_{net}^{-1} in 2020.² Nevertheless, the latter is still more than twice the US Department of Energy's ultimate goal of 30 US\$ kW_{net}^{-1} .² To

help reaching this goal, one key strategy is to replace Pt as the catalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), with earth-abundant catalysts without compromising the performance as well as the durability.

Emerging as a promising platinum group metal (PGM)-free candidate for catalyzing ORR in the fuel cell cathodes, Fe–N–C catalysts have reached application-relevant activities, some kinetic descriptors being comparable to those achieved with Pt/C catalysts, yet their durability still requires a critical improvement, especially in acidic media.³ Low durability is

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perhaps the main roadblock that currently limits the successful commercial application of such catalysts in PEMFCs.³ A potential strategy is to use metal–N–C materials as a support for Pt particles to improve both the activity and stability of the PGM catalysts.⁴ Otherwise, to directly apply Fe–N–C materials as the ORR catalysts, an advanced understanding of their degradation mechanisms is required to develop more durable materials or stabilize the existing ones. However, fundamental studies aiming at obtaining such knowledge are hindered by the system's complexity. For instance, the various Fe species, such as graphene-covered Fe carbide particles and atomically dispersed FeN₄C_y sites, may contribute to the ORR activity and suffer from degradation differently.^{5,6} Even among FeN₄C_y sites, at least two distinct kinds were identified. The FeN₄C₁₂ sites (site S1/doublet labeled D1 in Mössbauer spectra) where Fe is coordinated to four pyrrolic N (N_{pyrrolic}) are more active but less durable, while the FeN₄C₁₀ sites (site S2/doublet D2 in Mössbauer spectra) where Fe is coordinated to four pyridinic N (N_{pyridinic}) are less active but more durable in acidic media as well as in alkaline media.^{7,8} Based on this knowledge, a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) technique has been applied to convert some S1 into S2 sites in Fe–N–C catalysts, demonstrating improved durability in PEMFCs (>300 h at 0.67 V).⁹ Still, this is at least 1 order of magnitude shorter than the durability of stacks using Pt.² On the other hand, Fe–N–C catalysts are more durable in alkaline than in acidic media.¹⁰ Accompanying the rapid improvement of anion exchange membranes (AEMs),¹¹ durable and affordable AEMFCs may be a more feasible option. However, the voltage decay rate of AEMFCs with Fe–N–C cathodes is still around 1 order of magnitude higher (e.g., 460 μV/h at 600 mA cm⁻², H₂/O₂, 80 °C)¹² than that of AEMFCs using Pt cathodes (e.g., 15.36 μV/h at 600 mA cm⁻², H₂/O₂, 75 °C).¹³ This decay may be attributed to not only the degradation of the catalysts but also the degradation of the ionomers in the catalyst layers of cathodes due to low H₂O content.⁸ Thus, it would be fairer to compare the degradation of AEMFCs with different cathode catalysts but the same ionomer and similar water management conditions. This work contributes to the fundamental understanding of the degradation of Fe–N–C catalysts, and thus, their different degradation processes in various operation modes are summarized below.

Fe demetalation from the FeN₄C_y active sites is one of the main degradation processes. It is observed during both load cycling in rotating disk electrode (RDE) (between 0.6 and 1.0 V_{RHE}, Ar-saturated 0.1 M H₂SO₄, 80 °C) and steady-state operation mode in PEMFCs (0.5 or 0.6 V, 80 °C). The leaching of Fe has been directly correlated to performance loss.^{7,14,15} For the same catalyst, the Fe dissolution rate in alkaline media is lower than in acidic but still significant.¹⁰ In alkaline media, the cumulative ORR Faradaic charge was shown to highly correlate with the total dissolved amount of Fe, based on which the stability (S)-number was introduced.¹⁶ The dissolved Fe species may agglomerate,^{6,7,17,18} poison the PEM, and/or be released with exhaust water.¹⁹ Moreover, the simultaneous presence of Fe ions with the byproduct and intermediate of the ORR, H₂O₂, could further destabilize the Fe–N–C catalysts as H₂O₂ may undergo Fenton reactions with Fe species, producing reactive oxygen species (ROS). The H₂O₂ or ROS may oxidize the N–C matrix, leading to the formation of O-containing functional groups at a significant rate in acidic yet a slower rate in alkaline media. This modification can decrease the oxophilicity and, thus, the

turnover frequency (TOF) of otherwise structurally intact FeN_xC_y active sites.^{20–22}

Compared to the degradation during regular fuel cell operation, the degradation during start–stop events is more harmful to the Fe–N–C catalysts.^{14,23} During start–stop events, the C matrix and the N species may also undergo electrochemical oxidation, known as carbon corrosion (Reaction 1 and 2) and denitrogenation (Reaction 3), respectively. Their onset potentials (defined as potentials at which CO_x and NO_x products are experimentally measured) are all reported to be around 1.2 V_{RHE} at 25 °C.^{24,25} Thus, they both occur during start–stop events, when the Fe–N–C electrodes experience potentials up to 1.5 V_{RHE}.²⁶ Note that the free energy barrier (ΔE_b) of denitrogenation of N-doped C (Reaction 3) varies with the type of N species undergoing oxidation. For example, when the gaseous product was NO, the ΔE_b for denitrogenation of graphitic N (N_{graphitic}) and N_{pyridinic} (ΔE_b(N_{graphitic}) and ΔE_b(N_{pyridinic})), were calculated to be 10.3 and 6.26 eV, respectively.^{24,27,28}

Although both carbon corrosion and denitrogenation may jeopardize the integrity of the catalyst layers, most Fe–N–C studies focus on carbon corrosion in acidic media,^{14,23,29–31} while similar studies in the base are rare. However, according to the literature studying glassy carbon electrodes as a model system, the carbon corrosion mechanism varies with the pH of the electrolyte, and carbon corrosion in alkaline media leads to severe macroscopic degradation.³² We anticipate that also Fe–N–C degradation in the base may be significant. In the absence of related literature, we believe that the knowledge of the degradation in Fe–N–C catalysts during carbon corrosion in acidic media and experimental techniques used to accumulate this knowledge is valuable for the coming studies on alkaline systems and, thus, is discussed below.

In aqueous model systems (AMS), such as RDE and scanning flow cell (SFC), the rate of carbon corrosion in acidic media was shown to accelerate at elevated temperatures and/or higher anodic potentials.^{23,30} By coupling SFC to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS), it was demonstrated that the rate of Fe dissolution increases with the rate of carbon corrosion.²³ Carbon corrosion can also be traced *ex situ* using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy. For instance, the sum of the deconvoluted XPS N-1s signals associated with N-Metal (N_{Me}) and N_{pyridinic} was found to be positively correlated with the intensity of the D₃ band (~1495 cm⁻¹) normalized to that of the G band (~1580 cm⁻¹) (the intensity ratio D₃/G) in Raman spectra, highlighting the need for disordered carbon to host a high content of N and MeN_x active sites. The D₃/G ratio had decreased after start–stop accelerated stress tests (ASTs) (1.0–1.5 V_{RHE}), especially in acidic media.^{14,29} In

Scheme 1. Electrochemical Protocols Applied to the Fe–N–C Gas Diffusion Electrodes in O₂- (Orange) or Ar-Saturated (Blue) Environments in the Gas Diffusion Electrode Half-cell Coupled to the Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (GDE-ICP-MS)^a

^aNote that after the whole Ar-protocol (bottom, blue), a final activity test in O₂ was applied (bottom-right, orange).

PEMFCs, the loss of FeN₄C_y sites during a start–stop AST (0.9–1.4 V, 3 s steps, 80 °C) was verified *ex situ* using Mössbauer spectroscopy.³⁰

While carbon corrosion and its effect on the ORR has been studied in both AMS and FCs, direct comparison of data from both approaches and transfer of knowledge from model to applied systems is still difficult. Due to its intrinsic limitations, RDE cannot be used to study how carbon corrosion at high anodic potentials influences the ORR at high loads (high current densities). Even though it was shown that a start–stop AST (0.9–1.4 V, 3 s steps) applied in RDE and PEMFCs resulted in similar degradation in mass activity at 0.8 V_{RHE}, also mass-transport properties were affected, leading to exacerbated loss at high current. For example, the drop in cell voltage after 300 start–stop AST cycles in PEMFCs is at least four times higher at 100 mA cm⁻² than at 1 mA cm⁻².³⁰ Thus, the information in the kinetic-losses-dominant region we may obtain in AMS cannot help us predict the degradation degree at higher current regions, where the conductivity and the catalyst layers' structure play essential roles. In Fe–N–C cathodes of PEMFCs that suffered from carbon corrosion during start–stop ASTs, reduced electron conductivity,³⁰ dropped porosity, poorer connectivity, and increased roughness were reported.³¹ To sum up the benefits and limitations of AMS and FCs for studies on carbon corrosion in Fe–N–C catalysts, AMS may be coupled with ICP-MS to detect the online Fe dissolution triggered by electrochemical oxidations of the N–C matrix, but may not reveal (or may underestimate) the resulting drop in electrode performance at high current density. The latter information is crucial in studies on the impact of carbon corrosion and denitrogenation on performance in the whole current density region. On the other hand, while the latter information can be disclosed in FCs, the loss of Fe active sites may only be confirmed by post-mortem characterizations, such as Mössbauer spectroscopy. To over-

come these limitations, a gas diffusion electrode half-cell coupled with ICP-MS (GDE-ICP-MS) has been developed in our previous studies^{16,33} and can provide both online dissolution data and electrode performance up to –200 mA cm⁻².

This study reports on the application of GDE-ICP-MS to quantify the Fe dissolution rates from Fe–N–C alkaline catalyst layers in the potential range between 0.93 and 1.5 V_{RHE}, where the electrochemical oxidation of the N–C matrix is the underlying dominant degradation mechanism. We systematically investigate the effects of temperature and O₂ (O₂ or Ar in the gas phase) on the fates of various Fe and N species and the change in the ORR activity in the current density range up to –200 mA cm⁻². The results reveal that although carbon corrosion and denitrogenation are not O₂-dependent, the subsequent processes may be. Thus, the ORR performance in the ohmic/mass transport regions dropped much more after the degradation in the Ar atmosphere at 62 °C than that in O₂ at 62 °C, which could not have been uncovered if the experiment had been done in AMS. Also, this work has taken steps beyond our previous study that focused on the degradation occurring at potentials below 1.0 V_{RHE} at room temperature and on the effect of ORR on Fe demetalation.¹⁶

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. Electrode Preparation. The catalyst studied in this work is a commercial Fe–N–C catalyst (PMF-D14401, Lot 0222-01B, Pajarito Powder). The alkaline Fe–N–C catalyst layer was doctor-blade coated on a gas diffusion medium with a microporous layer (H23C8, Freudenberg, 3 × 3 cm², 213.5 ± 4.5 μm). The ink preparation and deposition procedures are reported in Section 1.1 of the Supporting Information (SI). The resulting catalyst layers comprise 70.0 ± 0.1 wt % of the Fe–N–C catalyst and 30.0 ± 0.1 wt % of a commercial

ionomer (Aemion HNN5-00-X, Iodide form, Ionomer). By weighing the gas diffusion media before and after the ink deposition and its drying process, the catalyst loadings were determined to be $0.72 \pm 0.08 \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Before electrochemical testing, the ionomer in the catalyst layer was ion-exchanged in 1 M KOH (EMSURE, Merck) for 3 h, and then washed with ultrapure water (Milli-QIQ 7000, Merck) thoroughly three times. After this procedure, the catalyst layer was kept wet (no extra drying procedure applied) in the air for a maximum of 3 h before the sample was assembled within a GDE half-cell.

2.2. GDE-ICP-MS Measurements. The online Fe dissolution was measured with a GDE half-cell coupled to an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (GDE-ICP-MS), illustrated in Scheme S1. The detailed methodology of GDE-ICP-MS can be found in our previous works.^{16,33} As the detection of ^{56}Fe species with the ICP-MS (PerkinElmer, NexION 350X) using Ar plasma may interfere with $^{40}\text{Ar}^{16}\text{O}^+$, the instrument was operated in dynamic reaction cell mode using CH_4 (S.S, Air Liquide), which reacts exothermically with $^{40}\text{Ar}^{16}\text{O}^+$ but endothermically with $^{56}\text{Fe}^+$ (thermodynamically less favorable), leading to a higher ratio of $[\text{Fe}^+]/[\text{Ar}^{16}\text{O}^+]$. The internal standard solution monitoring the long-term status of ICP-MS and acidifying the alkaline electrolyte (0.1 M NaOH, Merck Suprapure) was $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Ge ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{GeF}_6$, Merck Centripur) in 1 wt % HNO_3 (ULTREX II, J.T.Baker). A five-point calibration curve was obtained with the blank electrolyte and four standard Fe solutions (0, 1, 5, 25, $100 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ L}^{-1}$) before every online measurement. To prepare the standard solutions, a middle standard with 10 mg L^{-1} Fe was first prepared by diluting the Merck Centripur ICP standard ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, 1000 mg L^{-1} , in 2–3% HNO_3) with 1 wt % HNO_3 . Then, the middle standard was further diluted to the targeted concentrations of the four standard solutions with the 0.1 M NaOH electrolyte. More details on the analysis of the dissolution data can be found in Sections 1.2 and 1.3 of the SI.

The electrochemical protocols applied on the Fe–N–C gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) in 0.1 M NaOH in the GDE half-cell are illustrated in Scheme 1. In the O_2 -saturated environment, the measurements were performed at both 22 and 62 °C (labeled as O_2 -RT and O_2 -HT, respectively). For O_2 -RT and O_2 -HT, the whole protocol consists of 5 subprotocols (see Scheme 1, top): (i) Cathodic steps_1, four 40-s galvanostatic steps from -5 to -200 mA cm^{-2} as the activity test of pristine samples and one final 40-s galvanostatic step at -5 mA cm^{-2} to track the degradation during this subprotocol; (ii) Anodic steps, six 40-s potentiostatic steps from 1.0 to 1.5 V_{RHE} ; (iii) Cathodic steps_2, repeating Cathodic steps_1; (iv) Start–stop AST, 200 square cycles of 6s comprising 3s at 0.93 and 3s at 1.5 V_{RHE} ; (v) Cathodic steps_3, repeating Cathodic steps_1. All the cathodic steps and anodic steps are separated by a potentiostatic step at 0.93 V_{RHE} as a near open circuit potential to clearly time-separate the dissolution peaks resulting from the various applied current densities/potentials. At 62 °C, an Ar-HT protocol shown in Scheme 1 bottom was applied to fresh GDE samples in Ar (blue), followed by a final activity test in O_2 (orange) mimicking the one applied during the O_2 protocol. Using potentiostatic technique, the Ar-HT protocol also comprises 5 subprotocols: (i) Cathodic steps_1, mimicking the potential that the GDE samples experience during Cathodic steps_1 in O_2 -HT; (ii) Anodic steps, same as the Anodic steps subprotocol in O_2 ; (iii) Cathodic steps_2, repeating Cathodic

steps_1 in Ar-HT; (iv) Start–stop AST, same as the Start–stop AST subprotocol in O_2 ; (v) Cathodic steps_3, repeating Cathodic steps_1 in Ar-HT. The three sets of online experiments (O_2 -RT, O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT) were all performed at least twice, every time on a fresh sample, to verify the reproducibility of the results. Please note that cyclic voltammetry (CV) before and after the degradation protocols were not included in the online electrochemical protocols because inactive or less active Fe species may dissolve during CVs. If CVs were applied before the whole protocol, an undesired background increase would lower the detection sensitivity while obtaining the more crucial online Fe dissolution data. If CVs were applied after the whole protocol, the Fe species that potentially redeposited back to the catalyst layers during the degradation might dissolve during the CVs, and then might not be observed by post-mortem characterization techniques, such as scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). Nevertheless, a CV (scan rate: 50 mV s^{-1}) of a pristine sample in Ar-saturated 0.1 M NaOH at RT is provided in Figure S3, which barely shows the Fe redox peaks. The potential data of the CV was 100% *iR*-corrected (80% *in situ* and 20% post *iR*-correction).

For the high-temperature measurements, the purged gases were heated up to 60 °C through a gas humidification system (01302019LFHS, Fuel Cell Technologies, Inc.). Also, the half-cell was heated up to 62 ± 2 °C by recirculating the electrolyte from the cell through a heating bath (AQUALINE AL25, LAUDA) and then back to the cell. Note that the tube used for recirculating the electrolyte during the online measurements was always washed with 100 mL ultrapure 1 wt % HNO_3 before and after the measurements so that the Fe species that stayed on the inner surface of the tube during the recirculation of the electrolyte throughout the measurements could be considered during the calculation of the collection efficiency (see Section 1.2 of the SI).

The electrochemical potential values are 100% *iR*-corrected and are reported with respect to a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE). Calibration of the reference electrode (Ag/AgCl Metrohm) was done every day at the temperature of interest ($E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} = 0.965 \pm 0.002 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 22 ± 2 °C; $0.955 \pm 0.005 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 51 ± 1 °C; $0.951 \pm 0.005 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 64 ± 1 °C). For the cathodic step-containing subprotocols in O_2 , the potential was 100% post-*iR*-corrected. Because the uncompensated resistance (R_u) may vary with the current density range and the resulting errors are magnified at higher current densities, the R_u was determined with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at each applied current density. Regarding the anodic steps and start–stop AST in the O_2 protocol and in the whole Ar protocol, the steady-state current densities remained always small enough, to allow the use of a single R_u , which was obtained at 0.93 V_{RHE} before each subprotocol and was used for the 50% *in situ* and 50% post *iR*-correction of the whole subprotocol. A detailed analysis of the electrochemical data during the start–stop AST is in Section 1.4 of the SI. An Ir/Ta mixed metal oxide was used as the counter electrode (METAKEM). The serpentine flow field was machined through titanium and plated with gold. The geometric area of the catalyst layer is 2.01 cm^2 . The gas flow rate of O_2 or Ar through the gas flow field was 50 mL min^{-1} , and during all experiments, there was an additional 50 mL min^{-1} Ar flow purged into the electrolyte. The initial and final volumes of the electrolyte were 250 ± 10 and $200 \pm 15 \text{ mL}$, respectively, and the changes in the electrolyte volume during

the online measurements were due to the continuous extraction of the electrolyte near the surfaces of the catalyst layers at a flow rate of $0.190 \pm 0.005 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ into the ICP-MS. More details on the GDE half-cell and the GDE-ICP-MS setup can be found in our previous works.^{33,34}

The experimental sections of Mössbauer spectroscopy, XPS, Raman spectroscopy, STEM, and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) are provided in Sections 1.5–1.8 of the SI.

3. RESULTS

To understand how electrochemical oxidation of the N–C matrix of Fe–N–C catalysts leads to degradation, the GDE-ICP-MS setup is used to obtain both online Fe dissolution and the increase of overpotential at ORR current densities up to -200 mA cm^{-2} . Moreover, because ICP-MS does not provide information on the initial coordination of the dissolved Fe species, the Fe species in the studied pristine Fe–N–C catalyst powder are first identified with Mössbauer spectroscopy measured at 6 K. Only two doublets can be identified as D1 (52% of the absorption signal, S1, Fe–N₄, pyrrolic) and D2 (48%, S2, Fe–N₄, pyridinic), testifying that the catalyst contains mainly atomically dispersed Fe moieties (see Figure S4 and Table S3).

The electrochemical protocols (see Scheme 1) were applied in a GDE half-cell, where the mass transport limitation of the gas reactant is mitigated relative to RDE. For example, in the GDE half-cell, a high current density of -1 A cm^{-2} can be reached with the studied commercial Fe–N–C catalyst at room temperature in 1 M KOH electrolyte (see Figure 1A,

Figure 1. Tafel plots of the Fe–N–C gas diffusion electrodes in O₂ (A) at $22 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, in 1 M KOH (purple) and in 0.1 M NaOH (light gray) and (B) in 0.1 M NaOH, at $22 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (light gray) and $62 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (dark gray) in the gas diffusion electrode half-cell. All electrochemical potential values are 100% *iR*-corrected. The error bars represent the difference between the two repeat measurements for each condition.

purple). Meanwhile, coupling the GDE half-cell to ICP-MS provides information on online Fe dissolution. Yet, the maximum concentration of the electrolyte is limited to 0.1 M to avoid damaging the ICP-MS instrument. In this study, 0.1 M NaOH is used for the online dissolution measurements at 22 and 62 °C (see Figure 1B, light and dark gray, respectively). In addition to the restriction on the electrolyte concentration, the duration of the online measurement is also limited. Thus, the ORR activity test is simplified to 4 galvanostatic steps, from -5 to -200 mA cm^{-2} , corresponding typically to a potential range between 0.9 and $0.6 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. At room temperature and between -5 and -25 mA cm^{-2} , the potential at each current is similar in 1 M KOH and 0.1 M

NaOH. In contrast, between -25 and -200 mA cm^{-2} , the potential at each current is lower in 0.1 M NaOH than in 1 M KOH (see Figure 1A). The higher concentration of OH[−] improves the transport of OH[−] within the catalyst layer. Moreover, increased temperature improves the ORR performance (see Figure 1B).

It is expected that an increase in temperature also accelerates the rate of the electrochemical oxidation of C or N species, which compromises the integrity of the N–C matrix and, in turn, leads to the dissolution of the embedded Fe active sites.²³ In the potential range between 1.0 and $1.5 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, where carbon corrosion and denitrogenation are the dominant degradation mechanisms for Fe–N–C catalysts, we first compare the rates of Fe dissolution at 22 and 62 °C in an O₂-saturated environment, noted as O₂-RT (green) and O₂-HT (yellow), respectively (see Figure 2B). The onset potential E_{onset} defined as the potential at which the signal of Fe dissolution is more than three times the noise level, is around $1.1 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ at 62 °C and $1.2 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ at 22 °C. The latter is in agreement with the reported E_{onset} of carbon corrosion and denitrogenation in 0.1

Figure 2. Comparison of the online Fe dissolution from the Fe–N–C gas diffusion electrodes during six 40-s anodic potentiostatic holds (1.0 – $1.5 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$) in three conditions (i) O₂ at $62 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (HT) (yellow) (ii) Ar at $62 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (blue) (iii) O₂ at $22 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (RT) (green), using a GDE-ICP-MS setup. (A) Potential profile. Note that the current density profile is provided in Figure S5A. (B) Fe dissolution rate normalized to catalyst loading. The same data was also plotted in semilogarithmic scale in Figure S5C. For clarity of representation, the online Fe dissolution rate in Ar at $62 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during this subprotocol is omitted from (B) and provided in Figure S6. (C) The anodic charge densities integrated from the 40-s anodic steps at E in the current density profile in Figures S5A and S6A,D,G. (D) Integral of Fe online dissolution at each potentiostatic hold normalized to catalyst loading. The relative loss of Fe at each potentiostatic hold ($-\Delta m_{\text{Fe},E,40\text{s}}/m_{\text{Fe},0}$) is provided in Figure S7. The potential and Fe dissolution profiles in (A) and (B) are from one measurement in O₂-HT and O₂-RT. The error bars in (C) and (D) represent the difference between the two repeat measurements in each condition of interest.

Figure 3. Oxygen reduction reaction Tafel plots of the pristine (gray) and degraded Fe–N–C gas diffusion electrodes in 0.1 M NaOH at (A) 22 ± 2 °C or (B and C) 62 ± 2 °C. Green Tafel plots in (A): after the anodic steps (dashed line) and after the 200-cycle start–stop AST (solid line) in O_2 at 22 ± 2 °C (O_2 -RT). Yellow Tafel plots in (B): after the anodic steps (dashed line) and after the 200-cycle start–stop AST (solid line) in O_2 at 62 ± 2 °C (O_2 -HT). Blue Tafel plot in (C): after the whole Ar protocol at 62 ± 2 °C (Ar-HT). The error bars represent the difference between the two repeat measurements for each condition.

M KOH,²⁴ supporting the hypothesis that carbon corrosion and denitrogenation take place before direct Fe dissolution from FeN_4C_x , and that the degradation of the N–C support triggers indirect Fe dissolution in the studied potential range. Different from thermodynamic equilibrium potential, the E_{onset} shows the applied potential where the activation energy of the electrochemical reaction is overcome. Hence, it reflects the reaction kinetics. Compared to 22 °C, the lower E_{onset} at 62 °C indicates that the activation energy of Fe dissolution triggered by carbon corrosion and denitrogenation is overcome at a lower applied potential. Above the E_{onset} at a certain potential (e.g., $1.3 V_{RHE}$) the rate of Fe dissolution is drastically higher at 62 °C than at 22 °C, and so is the anodic charge density integrated from the current density profile of the 40-s potential step (see Figures 2C and S5A). This agrees with the understanding that a higher oxidation rate of the N–C matrix at a higher temperature could result in faster Fe dissolution.^{23,30} In addition to the temperature effect, the impact of the gas atmosphere (O_2 or Ar) on the degradation of Fe–N–C catalysts during start–stop events is also investigated at a relevant operating temperature (62 °C) in this work. Figure 2D shows the amounts of the dissolved Fe species during the 40-s anodic-potential holds in O_2 -RT, O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT (Ar-saturated environment at 62 °C) conditions, Figure S6 provides the Fe dissolution profile in Ar-HT during this subprotocol, and Figure S7 presents the relative losses of Fe during these steps in the three conditions. In the investigated potential range, the amount of Fe leached from the catalyst layers at 62 °C is independent of the gas atmosphere (see Figure 2D and Figure S6), and so is the integrated anodic charge density (see Figure 2C). This can be explained by the fact that electrochemical corrosion of the N–C matrix involves H_2O and not O_2 as an oxidant (see Reactions 1–3). In contrast, in the potential range between 0.57 and 0.87 V_{RHE} , the Fe dissolution from Fe–N–C catalysts has been reported to be significantly faster in the O_2 environment (the ORR occurring at such potentials in O_2) than in the Ar environment.¹⁶ Figure 2C,D show that the integrated anodic charge density and the rate of Fe dissolution both rise greatly from E_{onset} up to 1.4 V_{RHE} for all three conditions (O_2 -RT, O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT). At even higher potential, the integrated anodic charge density continues to rise dramatically while the increase in the Fe dissolution rate slows down. During this subprotocol, the relative loss of Fe ($-\Delta m_{Fe,A}/m_{Fe,0}$ where the subscript A refers to the Anodic steps subprotocol) from the

Fe–N–C catalyst layers was 2.8 ± 0.8 , 2.9 ± 0.6 , and $0.8 \pm 0.1\%$ in the O_2 -HT, Ar-HT, and O_2 -RT conditions, respectively. To further unveil mechanistic insights, a quantitative analysis of the amounts of dissolved Fe (from Figure 2D) normalized by the anodic charge passing during the 40-s potential holds (see Figure 2C) is carried out in the Section 4.4.

For O_2 -RT and O_2 -HT conditions, the change in ORR performance following the anodic steps and the start–stop AST could be sequentially tracked thanks to the Cathodic steps 1–2–3 (Scheme 1). The ORR performance measured at these cathodic steps is shown in Figure 3A,B for the O_2 -RT and O_2 -HT conditions, respectively. For the Ar-HT protocol, the ORR activity was measured only after the whole Ar protocol (see Figure 3C and Scheme 1, blue). In general, the overall degradation (Figure 3, solid color lines vs solid gray lines) is milder in O_2 -RT than in O_2 -HT, and almost comparable in the current density range from -5 to -25 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ between O_2 -HT and Ar-HT, but much severe at the current density beyond -25 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ in Ar-HT than in O_2 -HT. Moreover, the relative loss of the Fe content ($-\Delta m_{Fe,i}/m_{Fe,0}$, calculation provided in Section 1.3 of the SI) and the increase in the overpotential at -5 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ over each subprotocol in O_2 are presented in Figures S8 and S9, respectively. Figures 3, S8 and S9 show that the degradation in O_2 during the cathodic steps (Figures S8 and S9, purple, blue, and green) is negligible, while that during the six 40-s anodic steps (Figures S8 and S9, orange; Figure 3, dashed color lines vs solid gray lines) is noteworthy, compared to that during the AST (Figures S8 and S9, pink; Figure 3, solid color lines vs dashed color lines). On the other hand, in Ar, the degradation of Fe–N–C catalysts after the cathodic steps subprotocol has been reported as minor,¹⁶ so the degradation after the whole Ar protocol reflects mainly the losses caused by the combined effects of the anodic steps and the start–stop AST.

To establish and discuss structure–property trends, two electrochemical descriptors were defined. First, the absolute increase in overpotential at -5 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ measured during the first and last cathodic steps subprotocols was used as an ORR activity change descriptor, $\Delta\eta_k$, due to the lack or negligible effect of mass transport at such low current (see Figure 4A). In contrast, to assess the change in ORR performance at high current, the absolute increase in overpotential at -100 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ measured during the first and last cathodic steps subprotocols was chosen, labeled as $\Delta\eta_m$. This descriptor is

Figure 4. Increase of the absolute value of the ORR overpotential after the whole protocol (A) $\Delta\eta_k$ at -5 mA cm^{-2} and (D) $\Delta\eta_m$ at -100 mA cm^{-2} , representing the changes in the ORR performance in the kinetic, and the ohmic/mass transport regions, respectively. (B) Left y-axis and the bars without line pattern: the relative loss of the Fe content during the anodic steps and the start–stop AST subprotocols ($-(\Delta m_{\text{Fe,A}} + \Delta m_{\text{Fe,AST}})/m_{\text{Fe,0}}$), calculation provided in Section 1.3 of the SI. This is a factor related to the loss of active site density (SD) because the identified FeN_4C_y species are the main ORR active sites for such a FeN_4C_y -rich Fe–N–C catalyst. The right y-axis and the bars with line pattern: the increase of the oxygen content obtained from XPS analysis (see Figures S10–S12). The appearance of O-containing functional groups could lead to reduced turnover frequencies (TOFs) of remaining active sites nearby.²⁰ (C) Anodic charge density of a 40-s step at $1.4 V_{\text{RHE}}$, which is extracted from Figure 2C and chosen to represent the oxidation rate of N–C. (E) Relative drop of the area ratio of the fitting peak assigned to hydrogenated and protonated graphitic N^{35} to the N-1s spectrum ($N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr./N-1s}}$), suggesting the degradation degree of the N–C basal planes. The results were obtained from the XPS N-1s spectra (see Figures S12 and S13). (F) Relative loss of the capacitive charge over the 200-cycle start–stop AST, indicating the degree of surface degradation. The corresponding calculation is provided in Section 1.4 of the SI. The error bars in (A–D,F) represent the difference between the two repeat measurements for each condition.

controlled by ORR kinetics, ionic and O_2 transports. (see Figure 4D). Moreover, as the oxidation of the N–C matrix is the primary dominant degradation mechanism, the integrated anodic charge density at a 40-s step at $1.4 V_{\text{RHE}}$ ($Q_{1.4V,40s}$), extracted from Figure 2C and replotted in Figure 4C, was defined as a descriptor of the N–C oxidation rate. Additionally, post-mortem characterization was performed on the pristine electrodes and the samples that were degraded by the whole O_2 and Ar protocols shown in Scheme 1. Thus, we can discuss below in more depth the degradation mechanisms, which mainly took place in the anodic-step and AST subprotocols.

Representing the degradation in the kinetic region, the increase of the overpotential at -5 mA cm^{-2} in O_2 -HT is more than twice that in O_2 -RT, and is slightly lower than that in Ar-HT (considering the error bars). Generally, the overall loss of activity can be attributed to the loss of active sites (Fe) and/or decreased TOF of remaining active sites. To quantitatively compare the change in ORR activity to the relative loss of Fe content, the Fe content lost during the specific anodic steps and AST subprotocols was quantified (the calculation is provided in Section 1.3 of the SI), and the sum of the relative losses in Fe content during these two subprotocols ($-(\Delta m_{\text{Fe,A}} + \Delta m_{\text{Fe,AST}})/m_{\text{Fe,0}}$) was plotted in Figure 4B as the bars without line pattern. Comparing Figures 4A–C, 4B, and 4C, one can see that the trend of the relative loss of Fe during the 40-s anodic peaks and the start–stop AST resembles both trends of the increase in kinetic overpotential ($\Delta\eta_k$) and the oxidation rate of N–C ($Q_{1.4V,40s}$), $\text{Ar-HT} \approx \text{O}_2\text{-HT} > \text{O}_2\text{-RT}$. In addition to the loss of Fe active sites, a drop in the TOF of remaining sites also can contribute to a drop in the ORR

activity. As a decreased TOF has been correlated to more O-containing functional groups on the carbon surface,²⁰ XPS was performed to quantify the C, O, and N elements (see Figures S10–S12) and from these spectra, the elemental compositions of the Fe–N–C catalyst layers were calculated and provided in Table S4. Compared to the pristine sample, the increase in the O content of the GDEs after degradation in the three studied conditions was plotted in Figure 4B as the bars with a line pattern. Once more, comparing Figure 4A–C, the trend of the increase in the O content follows those of $\Delta\eta_k$ and $Q_{1.4V,40s}$, $\text{Ar-HT} \approx \text{O}_2\text{-HT} > \text{O}_2\text{-RT}$. Hence, the more severe degradation in the kinetic region at HT than at RT can be explained by combined increased losses of Fe active sites and decreased TOF, both being induced by carbon corrosion and denitrogenation. The slightly higher increase in overpotential at -5 mA cm^{-2} after Ar-HT than after O_2 -HT protocols suggests minor O_2 -dependent processes occurring during the electrochemical protocol.

The impact of such O_2 -dependent processes becomes more significant in the ohmic/mass transport regions (see Figure 3B,C). Hence, the information on the losses of active sites and their TOF is insufficient to explain the additional overpotential observed at -100 mA cm^{-2} after the Ar-HT protocol, compared to those in the O_2 atmosphere. Thus, a different restructuring of the catalyst layers has to be considered. First, although the averaged Raman spectra of the GDEs after the degradation protocols (see Figure S14) seem at first hand very similar to that of the pristine GDE, it is noteworthy that the intensities and the standard deviation obtained from multiple spectra acquisition at around 1495 cm^{-1} increase from the pristine electrode to O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT. The subtle increases

Figure 5. HAADF-STEM and EDX spectrum images of powders scratched from (A) pristine GDE, and GDEs degraded in (B) O₂-RT, (C) O₂-HT, and (D) Ar-HT conditions. Note that the magnifications of (A) and (D) are the same while those of (B) and (C) are bigger to show the features of the observed depositions. The line profile of the arrow in (B) is provided in Figure S16. The yellow dashed circles in (C) mark the observed Fe/O clusters. More images and EDXS data are provided in Section 2.7 of the SI.

of the averaged intensities at 1495 cm⁻¹ are still smaller than one standard deviation of the intensity at 1495 cm⁻¹ of the pristine GDE. A hidden peak centered at 1495 cm⁻¹ is usually assigned to the D₃-band, and its intensity normalized to that of the G band has been correlated to N_{pyridinic} + N_{Metal} in M–N–C materials.²⁹ Thus, the subtly increased average intensities and the expanded standard deviations at 1495 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectra of the samples degraded in O₂-HT and Ar-HT suggest heterogeneous degradation of the N_{pyridinic} and/or N_{Metal} in-plane or through-plane of the GDE at 62 °C. Namely, the degradation in those regions varies considerably from spot to spot. Moreover, during carbon corrosion, the formation of carbonate ions in alkaline media can induce the formation of Na₂CO₃ precipitates (see Reaction 4). The precipitate can block the pores in the catalyst layer, and thus decrease the accessibility of O₂ to active sites during the ORR.³⁶ Yet, the Raman spectra in Figure S14 show negligible peaks of Na₂CO₃ at 1080 cm⁻¹ after all protocols in this work,³⁷ suggesting that even if some Na₂CO₃ precipitates were formed, the amount was insignificant. Also, the precipitation is O₂-independent. Thus, although this phenomenon may contribute to the increase of overpotential at –100 mA cm⁻², it does not explain

the larger Δη_m after the Ar-HT protocol vs after the O₂-HT protocol.

On the contrary, Figure S12C,D show a noticeable difference between the XPS N-1s spectra of the catalyst layers degraded in the O₂-HT and Ar-HT protocols, suggesting O₂-dependent degradation of one or more N species. Thus, the N-1s spectra in Figure S12 were further deconvoluted into five peaks: (a) the blue peak centered at 402.3 eV, contributed by the hydrogenated and/or protonated graphitic N (N_{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}); (b) the yellow peak centered at 401.1 eV, contributed by N_{pyrrolic} and/or hydrogenated pyridinic N (N_{hyd.pyridinic}); (c) the purple peak centered at 400.0 eV, contributed by N_{hyd.pyridinic} on zigzag edges surrounded by CO_x (N_{hyd.pyridinic-COx}) and/or N_{pyridinic} on armchair edges neighboring COH, namely pyridonic N, (N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}), of which the assignment is discussed in the Section 4.1; (d) the green peak centered at 399.1 eV, contributed by Fe-bonded N (N_{Fe}) and/or N_{pyridinic}; and (e) the red peak centered at 397.5 eV, contributed by imine.^{35,38–41} The area fraction of each fitting peak (N_i/N-1s) is presented in Figure S13. These main N

species are on the edges of the N–C matrix, except for $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ and the N_{Fe} in the FeN_xC_y sites on basal planes. As N_{Fe} can be on edges or basal planes,⁴² the change in $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ can best represent the destruction of the basal planes. While the N–C oxidation rates in O_2 -HT and Ar-HT are similar (see $Q_{1.4\text{ V}, 40\text{ s}}$ in Figure 4C), a higher relative loss of $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}/N_{\text{1s}}$ is observed after the Ar-HT protocol than after the O_2 -HT protocol (see Figure 4E), suggesting that the N–C matrix around $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ (basal planes) were more destructed in Ar-HT than in O_2 -HT. In contrast, the N and/or C species of other parts of the N–C matrix were oxidized more frequently in O_2 -HT than in Ar-HT because the overall N–C oxidation rates in the two conditions were similar. This tendency for the N–C matrix around $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ to be oxidized more frequently in Ar-HT than in O_2 -HT is then compared with the reduced ORR performance in the ohmic/mass transport regions ($\Delta\eta_{\text{m}}$) in Figure 4D because repeated oxidations of N–C matrix to gaseous NO_x and CO_x could lead to poorer porosity and pore connectivity, and in turn, larger $\Delta\eta_{\text{m}}$.³¹ The $\Delta\eta_{\text{m}}$ after the Ar-HT protocol is at least twice larger than that after the O_2 -HT protocol (see Figure 4D), and the N–C oxidation that occurs around $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ (basal planes) was more pronounced in Ar-HT than in O_2 -HT. These results indicate that the repeated oxidations of the N–C basal planes could eventually severely degrade the catalyst layer structure, resulting in a large $\Delta\eta_{\text{m}}$. The degradation around $N_{\text{graphitic}}$ will be discussed in more detail in the Section 4.2.

Moreover, the relative changes in the capacitive charge throughout the start–stop AST vary with the studied conditions (see Figure 4F), indicating different degrees of surface degradation in the catalyst layers. The relative changes of capacitive charge were calculated from the current density data in the first and 200th cycles of the AST (detailed calculation is provided in Section 1.4 of the SI). For O_2 -RT, the capacitive charge barely changes or even slightly increases, which can be attributed to a moderate increase of O-containing functional groups (see Figure 4B).³² On the contrary, for both O_2 -HT and Ar-HT, the capacitive charge dramatically drops. Although the O-containing functional groups also increase in these two conditions at 62 °C (see Figure 4B), the reduced capacitive charges may be better explained by the notable destruction of the N–C matrix, suggested by the relative increase of the atomic ratio of N to C measured by XPS (noted as N-1s/C-1s), which are 5.5 and 6.5% after the O_2 -HT and Ar-HT protocols, respectively, compared to –0.2% after the O_2 -RT protocol (see Figure S15). The relative increase of N-1s/C-1s also indicates that carbon corrosion is more favorable/rapid than denitrogenation. Furthermore, the capacitive charge declines 13% more in Ar-HT than O_2 -HT, which coincides with the more remarkable loss of the $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ and more pronounced degradation in Ar (see Figure 4D,E).

In addition to the destruction of the N–C matrix, the appearance of Fe redepositions is also shown to be O_2 -dependent in the TEM images in Figures 5 and S17. In particular, Figure 5B,C show evident redepositions of dissolved Fe species after the whole O_2 protocol at both RT and HT, respectively, while after the Ar-HT protocol, Fe redeposition is barely noticeable using TEM, e.g., Figure 5D. Moreover, the forms of the deposition vary with the operating temperature. In the O_2 atmosphere, Fe particles were observed after the protocol at room temperature, whereas at 62 °C, Fe/O clusters were noted (see Figure 5B,C, respectively).¹⁷ The Fe particles formed in the O_2 -RT condition might be diverse because the

line profiles of some Fe particles do not show an increase of O signals with the increased Fe signals (see Figures S16 and S17E), while some others are suggested as Fe_2O_3 by their electron diffraction pattern (see Figure S18D).⁴³ The Fe clusters noted in the O_2 -HT condition are located closely to the intensified O signals in the EDXS images in Figure 5C. This indicates either the Fe clusters were formed close to oxidized N–C sites or that FeO_x clusters were formed. In the literature, Fe redeposition was not observed after a start–stop AST at 80 °C (1.0–1.5 V_{RHE} , 500 square cycles, 3 s holding time) in either O_2 - or Ar-saturated 0.1 M H_2SO_4 in RDE.¹⁸ Compared to this literature, the higher tendency for Fe redeposition in this work could be first attributed to the higher pH environment (0.1 M NaOH). Yet, this explanation might be oversimplified because the deposition process may also be influenced by other factors, such as the porous structures of the catalysts/catalyst layers, or the potential limits of the AST. Indeed, instead of 1.0 V_{RHE} , the lower potential limit of the AST in this study was 0.93 V_{RHE} . The steps at 0.93 V_{RHE} might be where the Fe redeposition process occurred, as suggested by the online Fe dissolution profiles during the start–stop AST in Ar-HT and O_2 -HT (see Figure S19B). In Figure S19B, the baselines connecting the background before and after the AST are presented as dashed lines. When Fe dissolution occurs, the baseline slope is usually positive, reflecting the increased background of Fe concentration, as observed during the AST in Ar-HT. While the amounts of Fe dissolution during start–stop AST are comparable in Ar-HT and O_2 -HT (see Figure S8), the baseline slopes are negative in O_2 -HT. The decreasing Fe concentration after the start–stop AST in O_2 -HT at 0.93 V_{RHE} hints that Fe could redeposit at this potential in O_2 -HT, where slow ORR still occurs. This aligns with literature where Fe oxide particles were formed in the ORR condition, in PEMFCs⁷ and RDE, reported in both acidic¹⁸ and alkaline media.⁶ As Fe oxide is active for ORR in alkaline media and may have a synergetic effect with the remaining FeN_4C_y active sites,⁶ the Fe deposition in O_2 may assist the retention of the ORR performance in alkaline media, explaining the slightly milder degradation in the kinetic region in O_2 -HT than in Ar-HT (see Figure 4A). More details rationalizing this phenomenon are in the Section 4.3.

To provide an overview of both Fe dissolution and Fe deposition during the O_2 -HT and Ar-HT protocols, it is necessary to note when these phenomena occurred throughout the protocols. Figure S8 shows that during both O_2 -HT and Ar-HT protocols, Fe species mainly dissolved during the 40-s anodic steps and the start–stop AST, the sum of which relative to the initial Fe content was reported independent of the presence of O_2 in Figure 4B. On the contrary, while the TEM images in Figure 5C,D show that Fe species mainly deposited in the presence of O_2 , they cannot reveal when Fe deposition occurred during the protocols. Fortunately, as discussed before, some hints were given in the Fe dissolution profiles during and right after the ASTs in Ar-HT and O_2 -HT (see Figure S19B). While Figure S19B presents the Fe leaching rate $\text{pg}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$, calculated from the Fe concentration of the extracted electrolyte $\mu\text{g}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ L}^{-1}$ with eq S4, the Fe concentration carries better physical meaning when the background of the profiles is being discussed. As expected for the case of Fe dissolution, the Fe concentration background increased after the AST in Ar-HT. Although the amount of the dissolved Fe was O_2 -independent during the start–stop AST (see Figure S8, pink), the Fe concentration after the AST at

0.93 V_{RHE} in O_2 -HT was, however, dropping below the background before the AST (also at 0.93 V_{RHE}). This observation indicates that Fe was redepositing in O_2 -HT after the AST at 0.93 V_{RHE} , which the integration of Fe dissolution peaks cannot take into account. Considering the amounts of Fe species leaving the Fe–N–C catalyst layers being minor during the 40-s cathodic steps, similar in O_2 -HT and Ar-HT during both the anodic steps and the start–stop AST subprotocols, but less at the 0.93 V_{RHE} step after the start–stop AST in O_2 -HT than in Ar-HT, the overall amount of Fe species leaving the catalyst layers during the whole O_2 -HT protocol should be smaller than that during the whole Ar-HT protocol.

To summarize, although O_2 does not influence the kinetics of the electrochemical oxidation of the N–C matrix, the more retained ORR performance at -100 mA cm^{-2} after AST in O_2 vs in Ar environment may be attributed to the presence of the Fe depositions that potentially act as active sites, and/or the less destructed N–C basal plane structure after the O_2 -HT protocol vs after the Ar-HT protocol.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Additional N Species after the Degradation. After rationalizing the different degrees of degradation in the studied conditions with the online Fe dissolution data and post-mortem analyses, it is still not clear why the N–C basal plane structure is less damaged and the dissolved Fe species are more prone to deposit in the presence of O_2 . Yet, before these questions are addressed, it is worth noting the clear appearance of a peak in the XPS N-1s spectra centered at 400.0 eV (see Figure S12) after the electrochemical protocols (Scheme 1). Figure 6 shows the area ratios of this peak to the whole N-1s

Figure 6. Ratios of $N_{400.0 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$, obtained from XPS N-1s spectra (Figure S12), before (pristine) and after the degradation protocols, as shown in Scheme 1, in O_2 -RT, O_2 -HT, and Ar-HT conditions. The peak centered at 400.0 eV ($N_{400.0 \text{ eV}}$) is mainly contributed by hydrogenated pyridinic N_{zigzag} surrounded by CO_x ($N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$)^{35,44} and pyridinic N_{armchair} neighboring COH, namely pyridonic N ($N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$).³⁸

spectrum ($N_{400.0 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$) of the pristine and degraded samples. Before further discussion, note that the comparison of $N_i/N\text{-1s}$ is fair only when the relative increases of N-1s/C-1s in Figure S15 are similar. For example, the comparison of $N_i/N\text{-1s}$ between the cases in O_2 -HT and Ar-HT is meaningful but that between Ar-HT and O_2 -RT is not. Interestingly, Figure 6 shows that the ratio $N_{400.0 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$ is higher after the protocols in O_2 -HT than in Ar-HT. As the amount of such N species is O_2 -dependent, it might be related to other O_2 -relevant observations. However, careful discussion over what

these N species could be must be made because many N species could contribute to this peak ($\sim 400.0 \text{ eV}$), such as two graphitic N within an aromatic ring,³⁵ $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$ (hydrogenated pyridinic N on zigzag edge surrounded by carbon oxide groups),⁴⁴ and $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ (pyridinic N on armchair edge neighboring a C–OH group, named pyridonic N).³⁸ Because the peak appeared after the degradation protocol, it is reasonable to assume that the N species that contribute to this peak would be degraded or modified from those existing in the pristine sample. Thus, $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$ and $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ are mainly considered. The former one is modified from $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ which initially contributed to the peak centered around 401.1 eV, overlaying with the contribution of N_{pyrrolic} (see Figure S12, yellow). It is noteworthy that the resulting change in $N_{401.1 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$ is not further discussed in this work because the measured change could be a combined result of the above-mentioned modification, Fe dissolution from $\text{FeN}_4\text{C}_{12}$ sites (S1), and/or else. Nonetheless, the carbon oxide groups (C–C–OH/C–C = O) around the $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ on a zigzag edge could be formed mostly during carbon corrosion, which is independent of the presence of O_2 . This modification leads to a lower binding energy of electrons with the $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ (from around 401 to 400 eV).³⁵ Thus, after the modification, the $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ is less tolerant against being oxidized. On the other hand, $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ is adapted from $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$ on the armchair edge that was initially assigned to a peak centered at 399.1 eV, overlaying with the contribution of FeN_x (see Figure S12, green). Once again, the resulting change of $N_{399.1 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$ is not further discussed because the measured change could be a collective consequence of the mentioned modification, Fe dissolution from $\text{FeN}_4\text{C}_{10}$ sites (S2), and/or carbon corrosion in the graphitic N–C regions, the latter of which is further discussed in Section 4.2. Nevertheless, the carbon neighboring a $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$ ($C_{\text{pyridinic}}$) on an armchair edge has been reported as ORR active.³⁸ When the ORR on such an active site is incomplete, an OH group may still be bonded to the carbon active site, turning the neighboring $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$ ($\sim 399.1 \text{ eV}$) into a $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ ($\sim 400 \text{ eV}$).³⁸ According to the increase in binding energy, $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ is more robust against being oxidized than before the modification. Although both the $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$ and $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ may be present in the samples degraded in Ar-HT, O_2 -HT, and O_2 -RT, their contributions to the peak at 400 eV would be different. Carbon corrosion at a higher temperature leads to a higher chance of creating the $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$. Additionally, at cathodic steps in O_2 , the ORR catalyzed by $C_{\text{pyridinic}}$ could transform the $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$ to $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$.³⁸ In other words, during the 1.5 V_{RHE} steps, the formation of $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$ is faster in both O_2 -HT and Ar-HT than that in O_2 -RT; and during the 0.93 V_{RHE} steps, the formation of $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ is at most possible in O_2 -HT and O_2 -RT but not in Ar-HT. Hence, the sum of the fractions of $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-COX}}$ and $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ or $N_{400 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$, is the highest after the O_2 -HT protocol (see Figure 6). The higher $N_{400 \text{ eV}}/N\text{-1s}$ after the O_2 -HT protocol than after the Ar-HT protocol can be mainly attributed to the formation of $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ during the O_2 -HT protocol, which is then discussed with other O_2 -dependent observations in the following sections.

4.2. Degradation of N–C Basal Planes during the Start–Stop AST. We have observed that the degradation in the ohmic/mass transport regions (see Figure 3B,C, $|j| > 2.5 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) is more severe in Ar-HT than in O_2 -HT. This can

be a result of the more pronounced repeated oxidations of N–C basal planes in Ar-HT than in O₂-HT, suggested by the greater loss of N_{hyd.gr./pro.gr.} after the Ar-HT protocol, but the reason for this tendency is still unclear. Another modification also depending on the presence of O₂ is the appearance of N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} mentioned in the Section 4.1. Although we are not sure if the appearance of the N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} species after O₂ protocols is fully responsible for the more retained structure around the graphitic N species in O₂-HT, we here propose a possible degradation pathway around the graphitic N–C region during the start–stop AST in O₂-HT and Ar-HT, based on the above-mentioned observation and literature.

In a N_{graphitic}-doped region (see Scheme 2), the oxidations of C bonded with N_{graphitic} (C_{graphitic}) have been calculated to be

Scheme 2. Degradation around the Graphitic N–C Matrix in Fe–N–C Catalysts during the Start–Stop AST^a

^a(A) Existing N and C species, which take part in the degradation processes. (B) In both O₂ and Ar, at 1.5 V_{RHE}, (i) carbon corrosion takes place around graphitic N, turning graphitic N into pyridinic N on an armchair edge.^{24,45} (C) In Ar at 1.5 V_{RHE}, there is (ii) oxidation of pyridinic N.²⁴ (D) In O₂ at 0.93 V_{RHE}, there is (iii) the oxygen reduction reaction catalyzed by a C neighboring a pyridinic N on an armchair edge, turning the pyridinic N into pyridonic N.³⁸ Or at 1.5 V_{RHE}, there is (ii) oxidation of pyridinic N.²⁴

thermodynamically more preferable than that of N_{graphitic} (see Scheme 2B-i).²⁴ Then, the loss of a C_{graphitic} species turns the N_{graphitic} into N_{pyridinic} and creates a defect. As C in defective areas is less stable than N_{pyridinic},⁴⁵ more carbon corrosion in the defective area (see Scheme 2B-i) may follow, turning zigzag edges into armchair edges in the defects.⁴⁵ Additionally, the oxidation of N_{pyridinic} is thermodynamically more preferable than that of C_{pyridinic} (C bonded with N_{pyridinic}).²⁴ So far, the oxidations are independent of the presence of O₂ as the oxidant is water. However, in O₂, in addition to being oxidized to NO_x at 1.5 V_{RHE} (see Scheme 2D-ii), the N_{pyridinic} on the armchair edge may also be converted into N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} during the step at 0.93 V_{RHE}, where slow ORR occurs (see Scheme 2D-iii).³⁸ Whereas during the Ar protocol, the N_{pyridinic} species is rarely modified into N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} but mostly

oxidized to NO_x (see Scheme 2C-ii), in line with the fact that the ORR barely occurs during the entire Ar protocol. The above-proposed degradation mechanisms in O₂ and Ar suggest that N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} is more probable to appear during the AST in O₂-HT than in Ar-HT. This can be supported by the higher ratio of N_{400.0 eV}/N-1s in the GDE degraded in O₂-HT than that in Ar-HT (see Figure 6), based on the previous discussion on the peak centered at 400.0 eV. Namely, the fitting peak centered at 400.0 eV in the N-1s spectra is mainly contributed by N_{hyd.pyridinic-COx} and N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} and mainly the latter appear during ORR.³⁸ Thus, N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} is the main suspect responsible for the higher ratio of N_{400.0 eV}/N-1s after the O₂-HT protocol vs after the Ar-HT protocol. The appearance of N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} could be crucial for slowing down the subsequent oxidation of the N–C matrix because N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} has a better resistance toward oxidation than N_{pyridinic} (the N species before the modification), indicated by N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}'s higher binding energy with electron (400.0 eV) than N_{pyridinic}'s with electron (399.1 eV). Thus, the sequenced oxidations of C_{graphitic} and its neighboring N–C (see Scheme 2) are more probable in the Ar atmosphere and destructive to the integrity of the N-doped graphene region, possibly leading to the mechanical detachment of carbon fragments containing other N_{graphitic} species.²⁴ This might explain the higher relative loss of N_{hyd.gr./pro.gr.} in Ar-HT than in O₂-HT (see Figure 4E).

4.3. Pyridonic N and Fe Deposition. Another observation potentially explaining the better retained ORR activity after the degradation protocol in O₂-HT than in Ar-HT (Scheme 1 and Figure 3B,C) is the Fe deposition observed in the samples degraded in O₂. As the types of Fe deposition formed in O₂ were diverse, the process might involve various mechanisms. For example, it could start with homogeneous nucleation and growth, and then, the particle or cluster adsorbed on the N–C matrix. However, the energy barrier for homogeneous nucleation is usually higher than for heterogeneous nucleation. Heterogeneous nucleation and growth could start from various species on the degraded N–C matrix. Among different possibilities, we here propose one where the presence of N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} in O₂ might assist the progress of Fe deposition during the start–stop AST.

Modified from either pre-existing N_{pyridinic} on an armchair edge or the ones degraded from N_{graphitic} or S2 Fe active sites after carbon corrosion, denitrogenation, and/or Fe dissolution (see Scheme 2B and 3B), N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} may appear during slow ORR at 0.93 V_{RHE} (see Scheme 3D-v).³⁸ The resistance of N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} toward denitrogenation is higher than N_{pyridinic} so the N_xC_y structure is more preserved in O₂ (compare Scheme 3C,D). Considering the potential interactions between N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} and dissolved Fe species, both the π -backbond and σ -bond between Fe and N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic} may be weaker than those between Fe and N_{pyridinic} because the additional OH group is an electron donating group, which increases the electron density of the N's p_z orbital (acceptor for Fe → N π backbonding) and lowers the electron density of the N's p_x orbital (donor for the Fe ← N σ bonding).⁴⁶ Nevertheless, compared to the more destroyed N_xC_y structure in Ar, where more N was oxidized to gaseous NO_x, the more preserved N_xC_y structure in O₂ may still have a better chance to form intermediates with the dissolved Fe species that have not diffused away. Such intermediates may serve as one kind of nuclei for Fe redeposition (see Scheme 2D-vi). Growing from such nuclei,

Scheme 3. Degradation around an S2 Site ($\text{FeN}_4\text{C}_{10}$)^a

^a(A) S2 site ($\text{FeN}_4\text{C}_{10}$). (B) In both O_2 and Ar, at $1.5 V_{\text{RHE}}$, the oxidations of N_{Fe} (i, denitrogenation) and/or the surrounding C (ii, carbon corrosion) lead to Fe dissolution (iii). (C) In Ar at $1.5 V_{\text{RHE}}$, there is (iv) oxidation of pyridinic N.²⁴ (D) In O_2 at $0.93 V_{\text{RHE}}$, there is (v) the oxygen reduction reaction catalyzed by a C neighboring a pyridinic N on an armchair edge, turning the pyridinic N into pyridonic N.³⁸ Next, the preserved pyridinic and pyridonic N may at least temporarily bond with the dissolved Fe and the intermediates may act as (vi) nuclei of Fe deposition.

the deposited Fe species might incorporate well back into the catalysts as shown in the STEM images in Figure 5B,C. In the process of nucleation and growth, the surface energy of nuclei determines the energy barrier of the whole process. Thus, even when the particle state is thermodynamically more favorable than the dissolved state, only the nuclei that survive the growth process before they reach a critical size, where the energy gain from the change of states compensates for the loss in maintaining the surface boundary between states, can continue to survive and/or grow thermodynamically favorably. Hence, having better survivable nuclei is beneficial to the whole redeposition process, and the number of the surviving nuclei usually determines the number of the particles, and thus, their sizes. Namely, when there are more nuclei, the resulting particles are more in number but smaller in size, and vice versa. Based on the above understanding, it is meaningful to check if the number of the proposed nuclei, which is indicated by the number of $\text{N}_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ correlates with the number of the observed Fe deposition at the varied temperatures in O_2 . At 62°C , there are more $\text{N}_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ species (see Figure 6), which suggests more Fe nuclei potentially being present. This is in consistent with the observation that the deposited Fe species at 62°C are more in number but smaller in size, observed as Fe/O clusters with STEM (see Figure 5C). On the other hand, at 22°C , fewer $\text{N}_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ species indicate fewer nuclei, agreeing with the observed Fe particles being less in number but larger in size. To sum up, the presence of $\text{N}_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ species in the O_2 condition might assist the preservation of the N–C structure and the nuclei formation for Fe deposition.

4.4. Anodic Charge-Normalized Fe Dissolution. In our previous work,¹⁶ the amount of Fe dissolution from an $\text{Fe}_3\text{C}@$ N–C-rich Fe–N–C catalyst during ORR in alkaline media at room temperature was found to be positively correlated to the ORR charge. Especially, the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution in the potential range $0.57\text{--}0.87 V_{\text{RHE}}$ is independent of the potential (see Figure S20B, gray), and a similar trend is also observed for the FeN_xC_y -rich Fe–N–C catalyst studied in this work (see Figure S20B, green). This analysis led to a more fundamental understanding of the Fe dissolution mechanism during ORR in alkaline media.¹⁶ Hence, to deepen the understanding of the degradation processes upon anodic polarization in this work, we revisit and quantitatively analyze the Fe dissolution result during the Anodic steps subprotocol by normalizing the amount of dissolved Fe of each 40-s step to the integrated anodic electric charge of the corresponding step (see Figures 2C,D and 7). In

Figure 7. Electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution at each 40-s anodic potentiostatic hold normalized to the catalyst loading. The integrated anodic charges during the 40-s anodic steps are provided in Figure 2C. Note that $E - E_{\text{onset}}$ is not overpotential because E_{onset} is not the thermodynamic equilibrium potential but is defined as the potential where the signal of Fe dissolution is more than three times the noise level. The measured E_{onset} is around $1.1 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 62°C and $1.2 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 22°C (see Figure 2D). The error bars represent the difference between the two repeat measurements for each condition.

all three studied conditions ($\text{O}_2\text{-RT}$, $\text{O}_2\text{-HT}$, Ar-HT), the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution climbs intensively as the potential increases, reaches a peak at $115 \pm 29 \text{ ng}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ C}^{-1} \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$ or $(2 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ mol}_{\text{e}}^{-1} \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$ at $E_{\text{onset}} + 0.2 V_{\text{RHE}}$ (E_{peak}), and then drops. Interestingly, the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution at both potentials $E_{\text{onset}} + 0.1$ and $E_{\text{onset}} + 0.2 V_{\text{RHE}}$ is similar in all three conditions, even including $\text{O}_2\text{-RT}$, testifying that the rate of Fe dissolution in this potential range positively correlates with the anodic charge. Namely, the absolute loss of Fe (at %) would correlate with the sum of the absolute losses of N and C (at %), assuming that the anodic charges were mostly contributed by the oxidation of the N–C matrix to gaseous NO_x and CO_x . Thus, it may provide a mechanistic understanding to analyze the quantities of the dissolved Fe and the integrated charge at E_{peak} . During the 40-s step at E_{peak} ($\sim 1.28 V_{\text{RHE}}$) at 62°C , the absolute loss of Fe ($-\Delta m_{\text{Fe},E_{\text{peak}},40\text{s}}$) is around $(4 \pm 1) \times 10^{14} \text{ atom}_{\text{Fe}} \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$, corresponding to a relative loss of Fe ($-\Delta m_{\text{Fe},E_{\text{peak}},40\text{s}}/m_{\text{Fe},0}$) of $0.57 \pm 0.14\%$, of which the calculation is shown in Section 1.3 in the SI. Meanwhile, by assuming the charges passing the GDE during the 40-s steps (see Figures 2C, S5A and S6A,D,G) are mainly contributed by

denitrogenation and carbon corrosion, and with the elemental composition obtained by XPS (Table S4), the estimated sum of the absolute losses of N and C is between 3.5×10^{17} and 7.0×10^{17} ($\text{atom}_{\text{N/C}} \text{mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$) at E_{peak} at 62 °C, corresponding to the sum of the relative losses of N and C being between 0.73% and 1.45%. The estimation varies by a maximum factor of 2 because the number of charges involved in the oxidation of a C or N depends on the products (2 for CO/NO, or 4 for CO₂/NO₂). From the above-mentioned calculation, the estimated sum of the absolute losses of N and C (3.5×10^{17} – 7.0×10^{17} $\text{atom}_{\text{N/C}} \text{mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$ at E_{peak} at 62 °C) is around 3 orders of magnitude higher than the absolute loss of Fe ($(4 \pm 1) \times 10^{14}$ $\text{atom}_{\text{Fe}} \text{mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}}^{-1}$). This difference confirms that the Fe dissolution during anodic steps could be induced either directly by the oxidation of N_{Fe} or N_{Fe}-bonded C (C_{N_{Fe}}) when the oxidations of other N and C species also occur or indirectly by the detachment of fractions containing Fe species due to multiple oxidations of N/C species in more distance. Moreover, with *ex situ* ICP-MS, the Fe content in the pristine Fe–N–C catalyst was obtained to be 0.65 wt % (see Section 1.3 of the SI). Based on this result and the elemental composition obtained with XPS in Table S4, the Fe content 0.65 wt % corresponds to 0.14 at%, which is around 700 times smaller than the sum of the N and C contents in the pristine Fe–N–C catalyst, 98.29 ± 0.07 at%. Hence, the relative loss of Fe ($0.57 \pm 0.14\%$, the 40-s step at E_{peak} at 62 °C) is actually in the same order of magnitude as the sum of the relative losses of N and C (0.73% – 1.45%). However, the latter is still moderately higher than the former because the charges of the denitrogenation and carbon corrosion are overestimated due to other contributions to the integrated anodic charge, such as the charges of oxidations of N–C to oxygen-containing functional groups and/or of oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Note that the Fe species in the pristine catalyst powder have been identified mostly to be atomically dispersed FeN₄C_y species (see Figure S4), which are not active for OER at potentials below 1.5 V.³⁰ Thus, the contribution of the OER to the anodic charge in the studied potential region can be considered minor before other Fe species that catalyze the OER appear during the degradation. For example, the Fe deposition observed in the STEM images of the sample degraded in O₂ (see Figures 5C, S17C and S18) could be FeO_x, which may catalyze the OER,^{47,48} and thus contribute to the anodic current. However, this contribution is also considered minor because this species is only observed in O₂ and barely in Ar, while the trends of the charge-normalized Fe dissolution in Figure 7 are similar in all three conditions. The trend of charge-normalized Fe dissolution can also offer mechanistic insights. As mentioned, different N and C species have various resistances against being oxidized. When the potential increases, a wider range of N or C species may be oxidized. Below E_{peak} , the climbing charge-normalized Fe dissolution with the increased potential suggests a growing contribution of Fe dissolution directly caused by the oxidation of N_{Fe} or C_{N_{Fe}}. Meanwhile, the oxidations of N_{pyridinic} and C_{graphitic} most probably also take place because they are easier to oxidize than N_{Fe}.^{24,29} Above E_{peak} , oxidations of other species that are harder to be oxidized may come into play, and thus, the increased charges do not proportionally lead to more Fe dissolution. Additionally, when a higher anodic potential induces more Fe dissolution (absolute value), the higher Fe concentration on the catalyst surface makes the reprecipitation more favorable and slows down the Fe dissolution rate.

Moreover, while the anodic steps are in an order where the less anodic/aggressive steps are followed by the more anodic/aggressive steps, the history effect may still exist because the oxidation of N–C can be easier in defective areas created in previous steps.⁴⁵ As these areas may have lost some Fe active sites, their oxidation in the following steps would contribute less to Fe dissolution, which could be another reason explaining the drop in the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution after E_{peak} .

Overall, the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution in the studied potential range, 1.0 to 1.5 V_{RHE}, varies with the composition of the N species in Fe–N–C catalysts and their electrochemical histories. However, the effects of these factors are minimized when the comparison of the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution is done with the same catalyst and at a certain $E + E_{\text{onset}}$, as shown in Figure 7. The closer the catalyst is to its pristine state, the fairer the comparison is. Thus, it is still meaningful that the values of the electric charge-normalized Fe dissolution at $E_{\text{onset}} + 0.1$ and $E_{\text{onset}} + 0.2$ V_{RHE} in the three studied conditions are similar, correlating the rate of Fe dissolution with that of the electrochemical oxidation of the N–C matrix as a function of $E_{\text{onset}} + E$.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This work investigates how O₂ and temperature influence the degradation of Fe–N–C alkaline catalyst layers in the potential range between 0.93 and 1.5 V_{RHE}, where carbon corrosion and denitrogenation initiate further degradation, such as Fe dissolution. We show that the online-measured Fe dissolution rate accelerates with increasing anodic potential and temperature, but is unaffected by the presence of O₂, which corresponds well with the kinetics of carbon corrosion and denitrogenation. The trends of the relative loss of Fe and the drop in the turnover frequency as well as the Fe redeposition during the electrochemical protocol with O₂ feed explain the trend of the degradation in the kinetic region. Additionally, in the ohmic and mass transport regions up to -200 mA cm^{-2} , the more retained ORR activity after the start–stop AST in O₂ is attributed to the more preserved N–C basal plane structure and the appearance of Fe deposition, which are both potentially related to the appearance of N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridinic} during the electrochemical protocol with O₂ feed. The Fe-free N_{pyridinic} on the armchair edge may be transformed to N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridinic} during the ORR at 0.93 V_{RHE}, or else be oxidized at 1.5 V_{RHE}. In contrast, in the Ar atmosphere, the N_{pyridinic} species are mostly going through the latter pathway, which explains the more degraded N_xC_y structure. Moreover, we hypothesize that the intermediates of the dissolved Fe bonding with the preserved N_{pyridinic-COH/pyridinic} species may serve as nuclei for further growth of Fe deposition. This work provides insights into the degradation mechanisms in Fe–N–C alkaline catalyst layers enduring anodic polarization, which may inspire the designs of less detrimental start–stop protocols or more robust Fe–N–C catalysts. For future works, more insights can be obtained by further coupling the GDE half-cell to other techniques, such as DEMS.

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■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

XPS data are available free of charge at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10794319.

Supporting Information

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Experimental details; Mössbauer spectrum; online Fe dissolution data and electrochemical results; XPS spectra; Raman spectra; atomic ratio of N to C; HAADF-STEM and STEM-EDXS results; and a detailed author contribution; and impact of carbon corrosion and denitrogenation on the deactivation of Fe–N–C catalysts in alkaline media (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

■ ABBREVIATIONS

GDE-ICP-MS, gas diffusion electrode half-cell coupled with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry; GDEs, gas diffusion electrodes; CV, cyclic voltammetry; RT, room temperature; HT, high temperature = 62 °C; PEFCs, polymer electrolyte fuel cells; PEMFCs, proton exchange membrane fuel cells; ORR, oxygen reduction reaction; PGM, platinum group metal; FeN₄C₁₂ site, S1; FeN₄C₁₀ site, S2; N_{pyrrolic}, pyrrolic N; N_{pyridinic}, pyridinic N; CVD, chemical vapor deposition; AEM, anion exchange membrane; RDE, rotating disk electrode; S-number, stability number; ROS, reactive oxygen species; TOF, turnover frequency; AMS, aqueous model systems; SFC, scanning flow cell; DEMS, differential electrochemical mass spectrometry; XPS, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; N_{Me}, metal-bonded N; ASTs, accelerated stress tests; SI, Supporting Information; RHE, reversible hydrogen electrode; R_u, uncompensated resistance; EIS, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy; STEM, scanning transmission electron microscopy; EDXS, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

copy; SD, site density; $N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ hydrogenated and protonated graphitic N; $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ hydrogenated pyridinic N; $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic-CO}_x}$ $N_{\text{hyd.pyridinic}}$ on zigzag edges surrounded by CO_x ; $N_{\text{pyridinic-COH/pyridonic}}$ $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$ on armchair edges neighboring COH, namely pyridonic N; N_{Fe} , Fe-bonded N; $N_{\text{graphitic}}$ graphitic N; $C_{\text{pyridinic}}$ C bonded with $N_{\text{pyridinic}}$; $N_{400.0\text{ eV}}$ the deconvoluted peak centered at 400.0 eV in a XPS N-1s spectrum; $C_{\text{graphitic}}$ C bonded with $N_{\text{graphitic}}$; $C_{\text{N-Fe}}$ N_{Fe} -bonded C; OER, oxygen evolution reaction

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